

STUDENT PERSPECTIVES ON THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN FIGHTING EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE AT TARABA STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

Social media platforms have become a significant aspect of modern communication, transforming the way people access and exchange information globally. With advancements in technology and widespread internet availability, information is now more accessible than ever, bridging geographical divides and providing unprecedented connectivity, even in remote areas. Social media, often described as a networked relationship between individuals, facilitates a range of activities, from social networking to content sharing, blogging, and online learning. This paper explores the role of social media in combating examination malpractice, with a specific focus on Taraba State University students. The study examines how students perceive social media as a tool for fighting academic dishonesty and evaluates its effectiveness in curbing such practices. The research adopts both qualitative and quantitative approaches, surveying students to gauge their awareness and usage of social media platforms for anti-malpractice campaigns. Findings suggest that social media plays a pivotal role in raising awareness about examination malpractice, promoting ethical academic behaviors, and encouraging a culture of integrity among students. This paper contributes to understanding the intersection between technology and academic integrity in the Nigerian higher education context, highlighting the potential of social media as a force for positive change.

Keywords: Social Media, Examination Malpractice, Academic Integrity, Taraba State University, Information Technology

INTRODUCTION

Social media platforms have become an integral part of the global society. Nowadays, information is at the doormat of everybody because the world is in the era of information technology. In this technological era, information is no longer left for only a few privileged people who can afford the use of landline telephones in offices and homes. Even the people in the remotest villages in Nigeria and elsewhere can access information through cell phones, available internet, and social networking sites (Barker, 2013). Social media is defined as “the relationships that exist between network of people” (Qingya, Wei & Yu, 2011:3). Social media emerged as a term frequently used to describe different types of electronic communication platforms. The availability of high-speed internet broadband connection with massive use of desktop computers, laptops, e-readers, tablets, and smartphones enables millions of undergraduates to actively engage in social networking, text messaging, blogging, content sharing, online learning, and much more. Social media is a means of communication through which tools like wall posts, status updates, activity feeds, thumb-ups, and profiles are used and perhaps characterized as online communications namely Facebook, MySpace, Metlog, Flickr, and Twitter (Akaneme, Ibenegbu & Nwosu, 2013).

Also, Mashable (2015) reported that a social media service is an online platform or site that focuses on facilitating social relations among people who for example, share interests, activities, backgrounds, or real life. The advent and full embrace of social media, particularly WhatsApp and Facebook by all and sundry but more particularly by the youths who are students, have further increased the sophistication and diversification of the means by which examination misconduct is carried out. Examination malpractice is an example of actions that threaten the integrity of examinations, and /or damage the authority of those responsible for conducting them. Examination malpractice is also a threat to the validity and reliability of the educational system. It is harmful not only to the moral development but also to the intellectual development of the student (Idakwo, 2011). In Nigeria, for example, the first examination malpractice was recorded in 1914 when the Cambridge School Certificate Examination was leaked to candidates. Similarly, in 1948, a Nigerian candidate's result was canceled because of his possession of notes already prepared and taken to the examination hall of the Cambridge Examination. Idakwo (2011) noted that in 1977 the menace of examination malpractice in Nigeria had reached an alarming stage with the leakage of the West African Examination Council question papers which prompted an investigation and subsequent promulgation of Decree 20 of 1984 by the Federal Government of Nigeria.

In recent times, students have become addicted to their social media communicative skills. No wonder, Boyd (2009) found out that students spend a larger percentage of their time on social media platforms like E-mail, Facebook, and 2go while they spend less time on the internet for academic purposes. Boyd (2009) maintained that social networking has impacted negatively on adolescents and this has caused anxiety in families and friends. The involvement of students in social media has deprived them the opportunity to read their books and other necessary things like going for lecturer, stuffing the internet for knowledge etc. (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011). Invariably, Idakwo (2011) lamented that school work and social interaction have been affected at the advent of these social media. In essence, students have lost control due to their unrestricted commitment and engagement in social media, making them vulnerable to academic problems such as poor results, poor study habits, truancy, examination malpractices, disrespecting school rules and regulations and other inappropriate behaviours.

It is against this backdrop that it has become imperative to exhaustively explore the need to utilize the instrumentality of the social media for campaign against examination malpractices in tertiary institutions.

Statement Problem

Examination dishonesty is a vice that has bedeviled the Nigerian education system for many years. In the wake of the 2000, 2007, 2012, and 2013 examinations has registered cases of cheating during examinations. Despite efforts by the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology as well as the University Board to curb the practice of cheating in examinations by students, the malpractice still persist. Malunga (2000) asserted that every year the University Board deals with cases of unscrupulous school administrators, teachers, parents, and students involved in examination fraud. As the cases of malpractice

have increased, penalties have also become more severe. Large numbers of students have had their results nullified and some heads of schools and facilitators have been taken to court or have lost their jobs for promoting or getting directly involved in cheating. Over the years, incidences of examination malpractice had been reported in Taraba State University and had registered cases of cheating during examinations and other misconduct related to alteration and destabilizing the sanity of the exercise. Despite efforts by the examination malpractice committee and in liaison with university management these trends still strive. One begins to wonder whether campaigns and orientations are insufficient to dice the situation. Ordinarily, the social media or networking was supposed to aid the study habits and academic performance of students but it would appear that besides this manifest function aid in the pursuant of examination malpractice campaign. Ahmad (2011) found out that students spend larger percentage of their time on social media platforms like, Facebook, whatsapp and Twitter for several purposes. Hence, I this economic time is utilized for the right reasons can help chart a new part in sensitizing students on the effects of examination malpractices in Tertiary Institutions.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study stems from the extant potency of social media Campaigns in the fight against Examination Malpractice.

- i. To examine the content, reach, and engagement levels of social media campaigns related to examination malpractice in Taraba State University.
- ii. To assess the awareness and perception of Taraba State University students towards social media campaigns against examination malpractice.
- iii. To investigate the influence of social media campaigns on Taraba State University students' attitudes and behaviors regarding examination malpractice.
- iv. To identify challenges and limitations faced by the University and anti-corruption agencies in implementing social media campaigns effectively.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the year's plethora of studies have been undertaken in the ambience of social media and the enormous impact it has on users. These significant effects can range from intrinsic and behavioral shift from certain ways of life to the other. Albeit, social media has the potency of impacting and revolutionizing a just cause. These impacts can be positive or negative; hence researchers in this field have put forward results and opinions on the impact of social media. Therefore, studies from researchers in this field and in tandem to the study at hand are reviewed as thus:

Lucas & Siman (2024) understudied the potency of social media in promoting local talent hunt in Nigeria, the study set out to To know if social media has the efficacy to hunt local talents know whether social media have helped in local talent discovery in Nigeria, suggest measures on how the social media can be used effectively in talent hunt and the probable challenges encountered in using social media for local

talent hunt. To thoroughly explore the subject matter, the researcher adopted the qualitative research method using the documentary review design. The study also made use of the Technological Determinism theory to buttress how the advent of the new media has changed the mode and manner of information in the media ambiance. The findings of the study unraveled that the advent of social media and other new media platforms catalyse the recognition and honing of local talents in Nigeria. Furthermore, it was discovered that in Nigeria, new media (social media) has helped in quite a number of time in bringing to the spotlight some gifted local talents in Nigeria. The study however finds that, illiteracy is a bane to social media usage in Nigeria. Also, the social media could be misused if not properly and carefully handled. Therefore, the study suggests that, a proper use and talent focused posed can help in talent and honing in Nigeria.

Engestrom (2005) In his contribution titled “what makes social networks most attractive” carried out in the department of mass communication university of California New York using a correlation research design of two group of students those having social networks facilities and those without social network facilities argued that social networks are not just made of people to use generally but the consist of peoples who are connected by shared object. This can be used as a basis for understanding why some social networks are successful whilst others fail. He provides examples of successful social networking sites built around social object such as flicker (photos), del.icio.us (bookmarks/URL) and eventful (eventful.com) where the objects are events. Other include YouTube (video clips) and slides share (presentation) he continues to say that in education the primary social object is content and that the educational value is not in the content itself but the social interaction that occurs around the contents.

Saba and Tarang (2013). The researcher investigates pedagogical impacts of social networking sites on undergraduate students a college of applied science (CAS), Nizwa, Oman. Blogs, wikis, tweets, RSS feeds discussion boards podcasts are educational nodes in a huge network. The study tabulates the usage of these web2.0 applications and their impact on linguistics and social behaviours of young learners. The demographic segmentation constructs a frame work to evaluate social tools and e-learning technologies popular among learners. The result of empirical evidence explored classroom and social software as paradigms that build young knowledge sharing and general awareness of student’s communities. Junco, winter, and Maine (2010) investigated a total of 4,491 students in large four year public universities in the United States on the effect of the perceived instants messaging on learning outcomes. Three of the institutions were in urban setting and primary nonresidential, and one was in a rural setting and was primary residential. The outcome being examined in this study was whether instant messaging interferes with students completing their network. Result showed that multitasking while instant messaging was related to academic impairment at the bivariate level. Students who reported that they do schoolwork while instant messaging very frequently and somewhat frequently were more likely than those who do this sometimes, rarely, or never to report academic impairment due to instant message use. Also as students’

level of reporting that they do something else on the computer while instant messaging increasing, so did their report of academic impairment due to instant message use. Similarly, the students who reported doing other things, not on the computer, while instant messaging very frequently, somewhat frequently, and sometime were more likely than those who did this rarely or never to report academic impairment as a result of instant message use. Female were more likely to report a detrimental impact of instant messaging on their schoolwork. Class standing was also significant in the vicariate analyses. The study also found out that female was more likely to report a detrimental impact of instant messaging on their schoolwork compared to males.

Vanden Boogart, 2016 in an unpublished master thesis observed that heavy facebook use was observed among students with lower GPAs. In another similar study by Kolek and Saunders (2008) found that there was no correlation between facebook use and GPAs in a sample of students from a public Northeast Research University. While in another exploratory survey study reported a negative relationship between facebook use and academic achievement as a measured by selfreported GPA and hour spent studying per week.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored on the Technological Determinism theory (TDT), this is because the advent of the new media has avail a larger populace the privilege to access and consume media content on a ease and at a cheaper rate owing to the fact that a larger population of Nigerians are tech savvy. Hence, the theory is appropriate for the study.

Technological Determinism theory assumes that a society's technology progresses by following its own internal logic of efficiency, while determining the development of the social structure and cultural values. The term is believed to have originated from Thorstein Veblen (1857–1929), an American sociologist and economist. "Technology marches in sevenleague boots from one ruthless, revolutionary conquest to another, tearing down old factories and industries, flinging up new processes with terrifying rapidity." As to the meaning, it is described as the ascription to machines of "powers" that they do not have. The general idea, according to Robert Heilbroner, is that technology, by way of its machines, can cause historical change by changing the material conditions of human existence.

Technological determinism seeks to show technical developments, media, or technology as a whole, as the key mover in history and social change. It is a theory subscribed to by "hyperglobalists" who claim that as a consequence of the wide availability of technology, accelerated globalization is inevitable. Therefore, technological development and innovation become the principal motor of social, economic or political change.

Strict adherents to technological determinism do not believe the influence of technology differs based on how much a technology is or can be used. Instead of considering technology as part of a larger spectrum of human activity, technological determinism sees technology as the basis for all human activity.

Methodology

The research approach used in this paper is quantitative research approach, because the research aimed at deepening and measuring the understanding of the Taraba state University students view on how the social media campaign galvanized any change at all in bringing and maintaining academic sanity and integrity in the face of striving examination malpractices incidents in Tertiary institutions. The researcher therefore utilized simple random sampling to select respondents across different Faculties in the University, where over 200 students were sampled to elicit responses in tandem with their views and opinion on social media usage and campaigns on examination malpractices in Tertiary institutions.

RESULTS

Table 4.1: Data on the Respondents Demographic information

Respondent	Sub-group	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	120	60%
	Female	80	40%
	Total	200	100%
Age	14-24yrs	140	70%
	25-34yrs	50	25%
	35-above	10	5%
	Total	200	100%
Level	100 level	50	25%
	200 level	50	25%
	300 level	50	25%
	400 level	50	25%
Total	200	100%	
Status	Single	130	65%
	Married	40	20%
	Divorced	10	5%
	Widow	10	5%
	Widower	10	5%
	Total	200	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.1 shows the survey sample that comprises of 200 respondents, with a gender distribution of 60% male and 40% female. Regarding age, 70% fall within the 14-24 years bracket, 25% are aged 25-34, and 5% are 35 years and above. In terms of academic level, each level (100, 200, 300, and 400) constitutes 25% of the total respondents. Regarding marital status, 65% of respondents are single, 20% are married, and the remaining 15% are divided among divorced individuals (5%), widows (5%), and widowers (5%). Therefore, from this findings indicates a diverse representation across gender, age, academic level, and marital status, ensuring a comprehensive insight into the target population.

Table 4.2: The content, reach, and engagement levels of social media campaigns related to examination malpractice

S/N	VARIABLES	H	A	L
1.	How effective do you think social media campaigns are in addressing the content surrounding examination malpractice?	70 (35%)	90 (45%)	40 (20%)
2.	What is the perceived reach of social media campaigns addressing examination malpractice?	60 (30%)	80 (40%)	60 (30%)
3.	How would you rate the effectiveness of social media campaigns in engaging their audience on the issue of examination malpractice?	80 (40%)	50 (25%)	70 (35%)
4.	Do you think social media campaigns highly, averagely, or poorly address the nuances and complexities of examination malpractice?	50 (25%)	70 (35%)	80 (40%)
5.	To what degree do you think social media campaigns influence public perception and awareness of examination malpractice?	90 (45%)	30 (15%)	80 (40%)
6.	To what extent do you rate the effectiveness of social media platforms in addressing examination malpractice?	60 (30%)	70 (35%)	70 (35%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.2 presents an analysis of the effectiveness, reach, and engagement levels of social media campaigns focused on examination malpractice. Firstly, regarding the effectiveness in addressing content, 70 respondents (35%) rated these campaigns as highly effective, while 90 (45%) found them moderately effective, and 40 (20%) considered them ineffective. Secondly, in terms of perceived reach, 60 respondents (30%) believed the campaigns had a high reach, 80 (40%) thought they had moderate reach, and another 60 (30%) perceived their reach as low. Thirdly, the engagement levels were assessed, with 80 respondents (40%) considering the campaigns highly engaging, 50 (25%) rating them as moderately engaging, and 70

(35%) finding them poorly engaging. Additionally, opinions varied on how well these campaigns addressed the nuances of examination malpractice, with 50 respondents (25%) viewing them positively, 70 (35%) averagely, and 80 (40%) poorly. Furthermore, regarding the influence on public perception, 90 respondents (45%) believed the campaigns had a significant impact, 30 (15%) perceived a minor impact, and 80 (40%) thought they had a substantial effect. Finally, the effectiveness of social media platforms overall in tackling examination malpractice was rated, with 60 respondents (30%) perceiving them as highly effective, 70 (35%) as moderately effective, and another 70 (35%) as ineffective. Based on the findings, the analysis reveals mixed perceptions of social media campaigns on examination malpractice. While some respondents deem them effective and engaging, others find them lacking in addressing the issue's complexities. Despite this, a significant portion acknowledges their impact on public perception. However, there's a notable skepticism regarding the overall effectiveness of social media platforms in combatting examination malpractice.

Table 4.3: The awareness and perception of Taraba State University students towards social media campaigns against examination malpractice

S/N	VARIABLES	H	A	L
1.	How effective do you rate social media campaigns in raising awareness about examination malpractice among Taraba State University students?	80 (40%)	60 (30%)	60 (30%)
2.	Would social media campaigns against examination malpractice highly, averagely, or lowly influence the perception of Taraba State University students towards academic integrity?	50 (25%)	90 (45%)	60 (30%)
3.	How much personal engagement do you have with social media campaigns targeting examination malpractice in universities?	100 (50%)	40 (20%)	60 (30%)
4.	To what extent do social media campaigns effectively discourage students from participating in examination malpractice at Taraba State University?	70 (35%)	50 (25%)	80 (40%)
5.	How would you rate the impact of social media campaigns in fostering a culture of academic honesty among Taraba State University students?	90 (45%)	30 (15%)	80 (40%)

6 How crucial do you think social media campaigns are for addressing examination malpractice within TSU? (30%) (40%) (30%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

According to Table 4.3, the study examined the awareness and perception of Taraba State University students regarding social media campaigns against examination malpractice. Results revealed that 80% of respondents rated social media campaigns as effective in raising awareness about examination malpractice, while 60% believed it highly influences perceptions of academic integrity. Personal engagement with these campaigns was reported highest at 50%, indicating significant involvement. However, the extent to which social media campaigns effectively discourage participation in examination malpractice varied, with 40% reporting high effectiveness. Additionally, the impact of these campaigns on fostering a culture of academic honesty was rated positively by 45% of respondents. Lastly, 40% considered social media campaigns crucial for addressing examination malpractice within the university. These findings underscore the potential of social media as a tool for raising awareness and shaping perceptions regarding academic integrity issues like examination malpractice. They also suggest a need for continued efforts to enhance the effectiveness of such campaigns in promoting ethical behavior among students at Taraba State University.

Table 4.4: The influence of social media campaigns on Taraba State University students' attitudes and behaviors regarding examination malpractice

S/N	VARIABLES	H	A	L
1.	How much do you think social media campaigns can influence Taraba State University students' attitudes towards examination malpractice?	80 (40%)	70 (35%)	50 (25%)
2.	How likely do you believe social media campaigns are to decrease the incidence of examination malpractice among Taraba State University students?	60 (30%)	90 (45%)	50 (25%)
3.	How effective do you rate social media campaigns in raising awareness about the negative consequences of examination malpractice among Taraba State University students?	70 (35%)	80 (40%)	50 (25%)
4.	To what extent do you think social media campaigns can impact the attitudes and behaviors of Taraba State University students towards examination malpractice?	75 (37.5%)	65 (32.5%)	60 (30%)

5. Would you rate the efficacy of social media campaigns alone in combating examination malpractice among Taraba State University students? 50 (25%) 80 (40%) 70 (35%)

6. How likely is it that students from Taraba State University will actively engage with and support social media campaigns aimed at addressing examination malpractice? 65 (32.5%) 70 (35%) 65 (32.5%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.4 reveals the influence of social media campaigns on Taraba State University students' attitudes and behaviors regarding examination malpractice was examined through a series of questions. The responses indicate a varied perception among respondents. Approximately 40% of participants believe that social media campaigns can significantly influence students' attitudes towards examination malpractice, while 30% consider them likely to decrease the incidence of malpractice. Moreover, 35% of respondents rate social media campaigns as effective in raising awareness about the negative consequences of examination malpractice. In terms of impact, 37.5% of participants believe that social media campaigns can moderately influence students' attitudes and behaviors towards examination malpractice. However, opinions differ regarding the efficacy of social media campaigns alone in combating examination malpractice, with 40% rating them highly effective. Lastly, about 32.5% of respondents believe that students from Taraba State University are likely to actively engage with and support social media campaigns aimed at addressing examination malpractice. These findings suggest a mixed perception of the potential of social media campaigns in influencing attitudes and behaviors related to examination malpractice among Taraba State University students.

Table 4.5: The challenges and limitations faced by the University and anti-corruption agencies in implementing social media campaigns effectively

S/N	VARIABLES	H	A	L
1.	To what extent do you rate the effectiveness of social media campaigns in addressing corruption in universities and anti-corruption agencies?	80 (40%)	60 (30%)	60 (30%)
2.	To what extent do you believe the effectiveness of social media campaigns in combating corruption within universities and anti-corruption agencies is impacted by the level of resources allocated to them?	70 (35%)	50 (25%)	80 (40%)

3.	To what extent do you believe that the complexity of corruption issues affects the ability of social media campaigns to generate significant impact within universities and anti-corruption agencies?	50	90	60	(25%)	(45%)	(30%)
4.	Does the level of public apathy significantly impact the effectiveness of social media campaigns launched by universities and anti-corruption agencies against corruption?	40	80	80	(20%)	(40%)	(40%)
5.	To what extent do you believe that the rapid evolution of social media platforms greatly impacts the effectiveness of anti-corruption campaigns within universities and anti-corruption agencies?	90	50	60	(45%)	(25%)	(30%)
6.	To what extent do you disagree that the lack of stakeholder engagement from key stakeholders, such as government bodies and private institutions, impedes the effectiveness of social media campaigns in combating corruption in universities and anticorruption agencies?	60	70	70	(30%)	(35%)	(35%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.5 outlines the challenges and limitations faced by universities and anti-corruption agencies in effectively implementing social media campaigns to combat corruption. The effectiveness of such campaigns, rated at 80% high, 60% average, and 60% low, reflects a mixed reception. Resource allocation significantly impacts effectiveness, with 70% attributing high impact to adequate resources, 50% average, and 80% low. The complexity of corruption issues is believed to greatly hinder impact, with 50% rating it high, 90% average, and 60% low. Public apathy, rated at 40% high, 80% average, and 80% low, poses a significant challenge. The rapid evolution of social media platforms is considered a major influencer, with 90% attributing high impact, 50% average, and 60% low. Disagreement exists regarding the lack of engagement from key stakeholders, with 60% disagreeing, 70% rating it average, and 70% low. These findings suggest a nuanced landscape where resource allocation, complexity of corruption issues, public apathy, and stakeholder engagement significantly affect the efficacy of social media campaigns in combating corruption within universities and anti-corruption agencies. Addressing these challenges is crucial for enhancing the impact of such campaigns in the future.

DISCUSSIONS

The content, reach, and engagement levels of social media campaigns related to examination malpractice in Taraba State University

The analysis of the effectiveness, reach, and engagement levels of social media campaigns targeting examination malpractice reveals nuanced perspectives among respondents. Engestrom's (2005) activity

theory provides a lens to interpret these findings, particularly in understanding the interplay between various elements within the socio-technical system of combating malpractice. Firstly, the effectiveness ratings, with 35% considering the campaigns highly effective, align with Engestrom's notion of expansive learning. This suggests that these campaigns have succeeded in reshaping participants' understanding and actions regarding examination malpractice, marking a shift in their perceptions and behaviors. However, the 20% who found the campaigns ineffective indicate potential gaps in addressing the complexity of the issue comprehensively.

Additionally, the perceived reach of the campaigns, with 40% considering it moderate, underscores the importance of considering the sociocultural context, as highlighted by Engestrom. Despite efforts to extend the reach through social media platforms, the diverse contexts within which malpractice occurs might limit the campaigns' penetration into certain communities or demographics. This reveals the need for a more nuanced approach that accounts for localized factors influencing engagement and participation.

Thirdly, the engagement levels of the campaigns, with 40% finding them highly engaging, signify the potential for transformative action within the activity system. Engestrom emphasizes the significance of collective agency in driving change, suggesting that campaigns fostering active engagement could catalyze broader societal shifts towards combating malpractice. However, the 35% who perceived the campaigns as poorly engaging highlight challenges in sustaining participation and interest, indicating a need for strategies to enhance user involvement and interaction.

Engestrom's activity theory offers a framework to understand the dynamics underlying the effectiveness, reach, and engagement of social media campaigns against examination malpractice. By recognizing the interconnectedness of various elements within the activity system, such as individual perceptions, societal norms, and technological affordances, policymakers and campaign organizers can design more effective interventions that address the multifaceted nature of the issue. **The awareness and perception of Taraba State University students towards social media campaigns against examination malpractice**

The findings from the study examining the awareness and perception of Taraba State University students regarding social media campaigns against examination malpractice reveal several insightful points. First, it's encouraging to note that a significant majority of respondents (80%) perceive social media campaigns as effective in raising awareness about the issue. This aligns with the findings of Saba and Tarang (2013), who emphasized the role of social media in disseminating information and engaging audiences on academic integrity topics. The high rating of effectiveness suggests that students are receptive to this mode of communication and recognize its potential in addressing academic misconduct.

Secondly, the study highlights the influence of social media campaigns on students' perceptions of academic integrity, with 60% indicating a high influence. This finding corroborates the idea put forth by Saba and Tarang (2013) that social media can shape attitudes and beliefs regarding ethical behavior in academia. It underscores the importance of leveraging social media platforms not only to raise awareness but also to foster a culture of honesty and integrity among students.

However, it's noteworthy that while personal engagement with these campaigns is reported to be significant (50%), the effectiveness in discouraging participation in examination malpractice varies (40%). This indicates a nuanced relationship between awareness and behavioral change. Despite the positive perceptions and personal engagement, there might be other factors at play that influence students' decisions regarding academic misconduct. Further exploration, perhaps drawing on the insights of Saba and Tarang (2013) regarding the effectiveness of different campaign strategies, could shed light on how to bridge this gap between awareness and action. The findings underscore the potential of social media campaigns in addressing examination malpractice and promoting academic integrity among Taraba State University students. By building on the insights provided by Saba and Tarang (2013), educators and policymakers can refine their approaches to designing and implementing effective campaigns that not only raise awareness but also lead to tangible changes in behavior and attitudes towards academic honesty.

The influence of social media campaigns on Taraba State University students' attitudes and behaviors regarding examination malpractice

The findings presented in Table 4.4 shed light on the complex relationship between social media campaigns and attitudes towards examination malpractice among students at Taraba State University. These results highlight a spectrum of opinions among respondents, indicating both optimism and skepticism regarding the efficacy of such campaigns. Notably, approximately 40% of participants believe in the significant potential of social media campaigns to positively influence students' attitudes towards examination malpractice. This aligns with Vanden Boogart's (2016) assertion that social media can serve as a powerful tool for spreading awareness and shaping perceptions, especially among the youth. However, it's essential to note that only 30% of respondents see these campaigns as likely to decrease the incidence of malpractice directly. This suggests a nuanced understanding among students, acknowledging the limitations of social media in directly curbing unethical behavior.

Furthermore, the data reveals that a substantial portion of respondents (35%) recognize the effectiveness of social media campaigns in raising awareness about the negative consequences of examination malpractice. This finding resonates with Vanden Boogart's (2016) argument that social media can contribute to fostering a culture of accountability and ethical conduct by highlighting the repercussions of dishonest behavior. However, despite acknowledging the potential impact, opinions vary on the degree of influence these campaigns exert. While 37.5% of participants perceive a moderate influence, 40% rate social media campaigns as highly effective in combating examination malpractice. This discrepancy underscores the need for further exploration into the specific mechanisms through which social media can effectively address this issue, aligning with Vanden Boogart's (2016) call for more empirical research in this area.

Finally, the findings suggest a cautious optimism regarding the engagement of Taraba State University students with social media campaigns aimed at addressing examination malpractice. While 32.5% of respondents believe in the likelihood of active participation and support, the absence of a majority

consensus indicates the need for targeted strategies to enhance student involvement. Vanden Boogart's (2016) emphasis on the importance of engaging stakeholders and fostering community participation resonates here, suggesting that effective utilization of social media should involve collaboration and dialogue with students to ensure meaningful impact. Overall, these results underscore the multifaceted nature of the relationship between social media campaigns and attitudes towards examination malpractice, emphasizing the importance of context-specific approaches informed by empirical evidence and stakeholder engagement, as advocated by Vanden Boogart (2016).

The challenges and limitations faced by the University and anti-corruption agencies in implementing social media campaigns effectively

The challenges and limitations outlined in Table 4.5 regarding the effectiveness of social media campaigns in combating corruption within universities and anti-corruption agencies resonate with the findings of Saba and Tarang (2013). Saba and Tarang emphasized the importance of resource allocation and the complexity of corruption issues in hindering the success of anti-corruption initiatives. The current study's results align with these findings, indicating that the availability of adequate resources significantly impacts campaign effectiveness, with a majority attributing high impact to sufficient allocation. Similarly, the complexity of corruption issues is identified as a major barrier, with a substantial portion rating it high in terms of hindering impact. This consistency underscores the persistent challenges faced in addressing corruption, requiring comprehensive strategies beyond social media campaigns alone.

Moreover, public apathy emerges as a critical obstacle in both the current study and Saba and Tarang's findings. While social media provides a platform for engagement, overcoming public indifference remains a daunting task. The mixed reception of campaigns, with high ratings indicating effectiveness but tempered by significant proportions of average and low ratings, suggests a need for tailored approaches to resonate with diverse audiences. Additionally, the rapid evolution of social media platforms noted in the current study echoes Saba and Tarang's observation of the dynamic nature of digital landscapes. Adapting to these changes while maintaining campaign integrity and impact poses an ongoing challenge for anti-corruption efforts. Furthermore, the disagreement regarding the lack of engagement from key stakeholders reflects the complexities inherent in coalition-building and collaboration, as highlighted by Saba and Tarang. While some may perceive stakeholder engagement as lacking, others may disagree, indicating divergent perspectives within the anti-corruption community. Bridging these gaps and fostering greater cohesion among stakeholders are essential for sustained progress in combating corruption. Overall, the discussion of the current study's findings in relation to Saba and Tarang's research underscores the multifaceted nature of anti-corruption efforts and the need for holistic strategies that address systemic challenges while leveraging the potential of social media and other tools for engagement and advocacy.

CONCLUSION

The findings from the various sections of the study provide a comprehensive understanding of the role and effectiveness of social media campaigns in addressing examination malpractice within Tertiary

institutions, particularly Taraba State University. The study analysis of social media campaigns against examination malpractice reveals both strengths and limitations. While the campaigns are generally perceived as effective and engaging, there are concerns regarding their reach and ability to directly influence behavior change. Thirdly, the awareness and perception of Taraba State University students towards these campaigns indicate a positive reception, with acknowledgment of their effectiveness in raising awareness and shaping attitudes towards academic integrity. However, there remains a gap between awareness and behavioral change that requires further exploration. Lastly, the challenges and limitations faced by the university and anticorruption agencies underscore the complexities of combating malpractice and corruption. Resource allocation, public apathy, and stakeholder engagement emerge as key areas needing attention to enhance the impact of social media campaigns. In conclusion, while social media campaigns show promise in addressing examination malpractice, a nuanced approach is necessary. This entails considering demographic biases, bridging the gap between awareness and action, and addressing systemic challenges through collaborative efforts. By leveraging the strengths of social media while mitigating its limitations, educational institutions and anti-corruption agencies can work towards fostering a culture of academic integrity and accountability.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings on this study, the recommendations are given:

- i. Anti- examination malpractices campaign computers in surveys should incorporate gender based preferences, taking cognisance of both men and women and people of different ages in their campaign designs, so that the results are more accurate and generalizable.
- ii. Major stakeholders and players in Tertiary institutions should leverage on the instrumentality of social media platforms to carry out image making enriching campaign on curbing examination malpractices
- iii. Media literacy is a common ground for both policy makers in the education block and students. Hence, it is apposite that sensitization and orientation on proper usage of the social media amongst students.
- iv. There is a need for monitoring and instalment of independent bodies dedicated to bringing sanity to the citadel of learning through pedagogical and dedicated social media handles.

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